

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center

Milestone 1 Target Enabling Package

Disrupted-in-Schizophrenia 1 (DISC1)

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Abstract

The Target Enablement to Accelerate Therapy Development for Alzheimer's Disease (TREAT-AD) centers were created to support the validation and development of promising new drug targets for Alzheimer's disease (AD) by providing high-quality research tools and technologies. The centers share data, methods, and both computational and experimental tools openly with the wider AD research community to aid in drug discovery and deepen understanding of the disease's complex biology. These resources are compiled into a Target Enabling Packages (TEPs) that are made available through the Synapse AD Knowledge Portal. This TEP focuses on Disrupted-in-Schizophrenia 1 (DISC1), a multifunctional scaffold protein originally linked to psychiatric disorders but increasingly implicated in neurodegenerative diseases, including AD.

Through an integrated computational and experimental pipeline, we systematically identified DISC1 (Disrupted-in-Schizophrenia 1) as a potential therapeutic target for AD. Single-cell RNA sequencing analysis of two independent AD datasets (Grubman et al. entorhinal cortex and Mathys et al. prefrontal cortex) combined with drug repurposing algorithms consistently identified trichostatin-A (TSA), a histone deacetylase inhibitor, as a top therapeutic candidate. Cross-dataset integration revealed DISC1 as the sole gene consistently upregulated across TSA-treated neurons, AD-associated neuronal populations, and protective microglial subtypes. Functional validation in human iPSC-derived cortical neurons demonstrated that TSA significantly upregulates DISC1 expression and maintains this protective effect in the presence of amyloid- β toxicity. DISC1 expression is notably downregulated in AD brains, and experimental evidence indicates that DISC1 restoration provides neuroprotection through multiple mechanisms including synaptic maintenance, mitochondrial function, and amyloid processing regulation. Comprehensive target assessment reveals DISC1 as a multifunctional scaffold protein with over 200 protein interactions, presenting both therapeutic opportunities and selectivity challenges. While DISC1 lacks direct enzymatic activity complicating traditional drug development approaches, its central role in neuronal homeostasis and consistent identification across independent computational analyses supports its prioritization as a mechanistically relevant therapeutic target for AD. This TEP provides the foundational evidence and strategic framework for advancing DISC1-directed therapeutic development in AD.

Introduction

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is one of the most pressing challenges in modern medicine, with current therapeutic approaches providing only modest symptomatic relief while failing to address the underlying pathophysiology that drives progressive neurodegeneration. The complexity of AD pathogenesis, involving amyloid- β accumulation, tau hyperphosphorylation, neuroinflammation, synaptic dysfunction, and mitochondrial impairment, necessitates innovative approaches to identify novel therapeutic targets and treatment strategies. Drug repurposing has emerged as a promising strategy for accelerating therapeutic development in neurodegenerative diseases, leveraging computational methods to identify existing compounds that may reverse disease-associated transcriptional signatures. This approach offers significant advantages in terms of reduced development timelines and established safety profiles, while providing mechanistic insights into potential therapeutic targets. The integration of high-dimensional transcriptomic datasets with computational drug discovery platforms enables systematic identification of compounds and their molecular targets that may have been overlooked in traditional drug development paradigms.

DISC1 represents an intriguing convergence point between psychiatric and neurodegenerative disease mechanisms. Originally identified through its association with schizophrenia and other major mental illnesses [1], DISC1 has more recently emerged as a potential factor in AD pathogenesis. The protein functions as a multifunctional scaffold, orchestrating diverse cellular processes including neurodevelopment, synaptic regulation, mitochondrial function, and intracellular signaling [2]. Critically, DISC1 expression is downregulated in AD brains [3, 4], and experimental evidence suggests that restoring DISC1 function may provide neuroprotective benefits through multiple complementary mechanisms.

We describe a systematic computational and experimental pipeline designed to identify and validate DISC1 as a therapeutic target for AD. This approach integrates single-cell RNA sequencing analysis across independent AD datasets, drug repurposing algorithms, cross-dataset validation, and functional studies in human iPSC-derived neuronal models. Through this comprehensive analysis, we demonstrate that trichostatin-A (TSA), a histone deacetylase inhibitor, consistently emerges as a top therapeutic candidate across multiple AD datasets, with DISC1 representing the sole gene consistently upregulated across all experimental conditions examined.

This document provides a comprehensive evaluation of DISC1 as a therapeutic target, encompassing biological rationale derived from computational analyses, structural considerations, expression profiling across tissues and cell types, regulatory network characterization, and assessment of druggability and assay development requirements. The evidence presented supports DISC1 as a mechanistically relevant target whose modulation may offer therapeutic benefits in AD through restoration of synaptic integrity, mitochondrial function, and cellular homeostasis. However, significant challenges remain regarding the development of selective modulators for this multifunctional scaffold protein, necessitating innovative approaches to therapeutic targeting.

Bioinformatics and Computational Biology (BCB) Core: Biological Rationale for Targeting DISC1 in AD

Computational Drug Repurposing and Cross-Dataset Integration Identifies DISC1

DISC1 was identified as a promising therapeutic target through an analytic pipeline integrating high-dimensional transcriptomic datasets with functional validation. This pipeline was developed to elucidate the molecular mechanisms and neuroprotective effects of potentially repurposable drugs for AD, including a histone deacetylase inhibitor (HDACi) called Trichostatin-a (TSA).

Figure 1 Single-cell analysis identifies TSA as top drug repurposing candidate across cortical brain regions **A**) UMAP projections of all cells derived from six control and six AD samples in the Grubman et al. dataset **B**) Pathway enrichment analysis highlighting key signaling pathways significantly enriched within each cell type cluster in the Grubman et al. dataset, with significance represented as $-\log_{10}(\text{FDR})$ **C**) Drug Score analysis for AD samples in the Grubman et al. dataset, displaying compounds with an FDR < 0.1 and a Drug Score ranking within the 90th percentile **D**) UMAP visualizations of all cells derived from 24 control and 24 AD samples in the Mathys et al. dataset, with distinct clusters representing cell types **E**) Pathway enrichment analysis highlighting key signaling pathways significantly enriched within each cell type cluster in the Mathys et al. dataset, with significance represented as $-\log_{10}(\text{FDR})$ **F**) Drug Score analysis for AD samples in the Mathys et al. dataset, displaying compounds with an FDR < 0.1 and Drug Score values within the 90th percentile. Cell type abbreviations: Ast, astrocytes; Dou, doublets; End,

endothelial cells; Ex, excitatory neurons; In, inhibitory neurons; Mic, microglia; Neu, neurons; Oli, oligodendrocytes; Opc, oligodendrocyte progenitor cells; Per, pericytes; unID, unidentified cells.

The analysis began with single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) data from two independent studies of AD-affected brain regions: the Grubman et al. [5] dataset (entorhinal cortex) and the Mathys et al. [6] dataset (prefrontal cortex). UMAP projections revealed distinct cellular populations in both the entorhinal cortex samples from six control and six AD patients (**Figure 1A**) and the prefrontal cortex samples from 24 control and 24 AD individuals (**Figure 1D**). Cell-type-specific differential expression profiles were computed using the Limma package, with pathway enrichment analysis highlighting key signaling pathways significantly enriched within each cell type cluster, including MAPK, PI3K-AKT, and cAMP signaling pathways in the Grubman dataset (**Figure 1B**) and cGMP-PKG, Oxytocin, and Neurotrophin signaling pathways in the Mathys dataset (**Figure 1E**). These profiles were then scored against over 21,000 perturbagens in the LINCS L1000 database using the ASGARD drug repurposing algorithm. TSA consistently ranked as a top candidate in both datasets, displaying compounds with an FDR < 0.1 and Drug Score ranking within the 90th percentile (**Figure 1C**, **Figure 1F**).

Using single cell data from Grubman et al. [5] 8 subclusters of neurons were identified (**Figure 2A**) that were frequently enriched for cells from AD samples (**Figure 2B**). The pipeline then leveraged Diagnostic Evidence Gauge of Single-cells (DEGAS) [7] to uncover neuron populations with high AD association scores within the scRNA-seq dataset (**Figure 2C**). Differential expression analysis between AD-associated and non-AD-associated neurons uncovered a TSA-enriched transcriptional signature that would not have been detected by bulk comparisons alone. Querying this AD-associated neuron-specific signature against the L1000CDS² tool again returned TSA as one of the most strongly predicted compounds. The L1000CDS² tool dataset is the LINCS L1000 small molecule expression profiles generated at the Broad Institute by the Connectivity Map Group [8].

Figure 2 DEGAS analysis of Grubman et al. neurons **A)** Seurat clusters of neurons **B)** Patient AD status of neurons **C)** DEGAS AD-association for individual neurons

To validate TSA's effects at a molecular level, differentially expressed gene (DEG) analysis was performed on hippocampal neurons treated with TSA versus DMSO controls (GSE189117). This analysis revealed robust transcriptional changes, with significant upregulation of genes involved

in neuronal development, differentiation, and synaptic plasticity (**Figure 3A**). *DISC1* was among the most significantly upregulated genes in response to TSA treatment ($\log_2FC > 2.5$, $FDR < 0.01$). Functional enrichment analysis of positively regulated DEGs highlighted biological processes with significant enrichment in neuronal differentiation, pattern specification, and cell fate commitment (**Figure 3B**), while negatively regulated genes showed significant reduction in pathways related to synaptic transmission and neurotransmitter release (**Figure 3C**). These results suggest that TSA modulates synaptic homeostasis while enhancing neurodevelopmental programs through epigenetic regulation.

Figure 3 Expression Analysis for TSA vs. DMSO Treatment **A)** Volcano plot depicting DEGs identified in the dataset. Genes with significant upregulation (positive \log_2 fold change) are shown in red, downregulated genes (negative \log_2 fold change) in blue, and non-significant genes in gray. **B)** Gene enrichment analysis of positively regulated DEGs highlighting biological processes with significant enrichment. Color intensity represents the false discovery rate (FDR) for each process. **C)** Gene enrichment analysis for negatively regulated DEGs, showing enriched biological processes with significant FDRs, represented by color.

A cross-dataset integration was then performed, intersecting DEGs from three sources: TSA-treated hippocampal neurons, AD-associated neurons (from DEGAS), and microglial subtypes identified in the Roussos single-cell dataset. This integrative analysis identified *DISC1* as the sole gene consistently upregulated across all three experimental conditions (**Figure 4A**), with quantification showing the intersection sizes and unique contributions from each dataset (**Figure 4B**). To confirm functional relevance, human iPSC-derived cortical neurons were subjected to TSA and $A\beta$ treatments, with viability assays demonstrating that TSA pre-treatment at optimal concentrations significantly improved neuronal survival when exposed to $A\beta$ oligomers (**Figure 4C**). Colocalization studies of synaptic markers PSD95 and Syn1 indicated that TSA pre-treatment mitigated $A\beta$ -induced synaptic toxicity (**Figure 4D**), with quantification showing increased synaptic clusters per dendrite length in TSA-treated conditions (**Figure 4E**).

Figure 4 TSA prevents A β -induced neurotoxicity and preserves synaptic integrity in human iPSC-derived cortical neurons while sharing key upregulated genes across multiple datasets. **A**) Overlapping differentially expressed genes (DEGs) between TSA-treated neurons (red, 5,015 unique genes), microglial subtypes from the Roussos dataset (blue, 419 unique genes), and AD-associated neurons identified via DEGAS analysis (green, 142 unique genes). The central intersection contains DISC1, upregulated across all three experimental conditions **B**) UpSet plot quantifying the size of each dataset (left bars) and their intersections (connected dots), highlighting the single gene (DISC1) shared across all three datasets **C**) MTS viability assay results showing the percentage of viable cells under different treatment conditions. Left panel: Neurons were treated with varying concentrations of A β oligomers (0.2 μ M, 1 μ M, 5 μ M). Right panel: Neurons were pre-treated with different concentrations of trichostatin-A (20 ng/ml, 60 ng/ml, 100 ng/ml) before exposure to 5 μ M A β oligomers **D**) Colocalization of synaptic markers PSD95 (red) and Syn1 (green) in neurons treated with 5 μ M A β oligomers and 60 ng/ml trichostatin-A. Images are shown for non-treated (NT), A β oligomers, and A β oligomers + trichostatin-A conditions **E**) Synaptic clusters per 20 μ m dendrite are quantified and displayed as the average per well (left) and as individual data points (right), demonstrating TSA's protective effect against A β -induced synaptic loss.

Transcriptomic profiling of iPSC-derived cortical neurons across treatment conditions revealed extensive differential gene expression, with 2,773 genes significantly upregulated and 3,167 genes downregulated in TSA-treated versus control neurons (**Figure 5A**). Most importantly, TSA significantly upregulated DISC1 expression ($\log_2FC = 0.65$, $p = 0.007$), and this upregulation persisted even in the presence of A β toxicity ($\log_2FC = 0.54$, $p = 0.021$), demonstrating DISC1's central role as a molecular responder to TSA (**Figure 5B**). Functional enrichment analysis revealed that genes upregulated by TSA treatment showed significant enrichment in biological processes critical for neuronal function, including synapse organization, modulation of chemical synaptic transmission, and axonogenesis (**Figure 5C**), with molecular function enrichment in tubulin binding, actin binding, and protein kinase activity (**Figure 5D**). Conversely, downregulated genes were enriched in ncRNA processing, cilium organization, and ribosome biogenesis (**Figure 5E**), with molecular functions related to catalytic activities acting on RNA and DNA (**Figure 5F**). Hierarchical clustering of the top 20 DEGs clearly separated TSA-treated samples from untreated samples, showing that TSA-treated neurons exhibited similar transcriptional profiles characterized by upregulation of neuroplasticity genes (**Figure 5G**).

Figure 5 Transcriptomic analysis of TSA effects on iPSC-derived cortical neurons reveals distinct gene expression patterns **A**) Volcano plot showing differentially expressed genes between control and TSA-treated neurons, with significantly upregulated genes in red and downregulated genes in blue **B**) DISC1 expression across treatment conditions shows significant upregulation in TSA-only and TSA-plus-Amyloid-beta conditions compared to Control and Amyloid-beta-only treatments **C**) Gene Ontology (GO) Biological Process enrichment analysis for upregulated genes in TSA-treated neurons, revealing pathways related to neural development and function **D**) GO Molecular Function enrichment for upregulated genes in TSA-treated neurons **E**) GO Biological Process enrichment for downregulated genes in TSA-treated neurons **F**) GO Molecular Function enrichment for downregulated genes in TSA-treated neurons **G**) Heatmap visualization of the top 20 differentially expressed genes across treatment conditions, with samples ordered by condition (Control, Amyloid-beta, TSA, Combined).

DISC1 Expression Profile Across Human Tissues

The DISC1 protein, encoded by the DISC1 gene, exhibits differential RNA expression levels across a variety of human tissues (**Figure 6**). The expression levels, measured in normalized transcripts per million (nTPM), are derived from RNA-seq data integrated from the Human Protein Atlas (HPA) and the Genotype-Tissue Expression (GTEx) project. An interesting feature of DISC1 expression is its highest enrichment in the retina, where it is markedly elevated compared to other tissues. This suggests a specialized role for DISC1 in visual processing and neuroretinal function. The retina's neural complexity and its connection to the central nervous system highlight a potential involvement of DISC1 in neurodevelopmental processes and sensory integration.

Figure 6 RNA expression of DISC1 in multiple tissues

Beyond the retina, moderate DISC1 expression is observed in various brain regions, including the cerebral cortex, hippocampus, and amygdala, indicating a potential but less dominant role in central nervous system function. The presence of DISC1 in the hippocampus, a region crucial for memory and learning, aligns with previous findings that link DISC1 dysfunction to cognitive deficits and neuropsychiatric disorders [9].

Outside of the nervous system, low to moderate expression is detected in reproductive tissues, adipose tissue, and certain immune-related organs such as the spleen and bone marrow. This broader tissue distribution suggests that DISC1 may have additional regulatory functions beyond neural activity, possibly influencing metabolic or immune-related pathways.

Given that AD is characterized by progressive neuronal loss, synaptic dysfunction, and neuroinflammation, the presence of DISC1 in key neural structures supports its potential relevance to AD pathology. Although its highest expression is in the retina, its presence in brain tissues, especially in regions involved in cognition, suggests that DISC1 may play a role in neuroprotective mechanisms. Furthermore, recent studies indicate that DISC1 is involved in synaptic maintenance, mitochondrial function, and intracellular signaling pathways that are disrupted in AD, making it an intriguing candidate for further investigation as a potential therapeutic target [10].

Regional Distribution of DISC1 in the Human Brain

DISC1 RNA levels are detectable across various brain regions (**Figure 7**), with DISC1 playing a well-established role in neurodevelopment, synaptic function, and neuronal signaling. DISC1 has been previously implicated in psychiatric and neurodegenerative disorders, including schizophrenia and AD, due to its involvement in intracellular signaling pathways and cytoskeletal regulation.

In the current dataset, the highest DISC1 RNA expression levels are observed in the white matter, thalamus, and pons, suggesting a significant functional role in these regions. The white matter, being primarily composed of myelinated axons, supports long-range neuronal connectivity, aligning with DISC1's role in microtubule-associated transport and neurodevelopmental processes [1, 11]. The thalamus, a major relay center for sensory and cognitive processing, and the pons, which is crucial for motor control and communication between brain regions, also

exhibit elevated DISC1 expression, reinforcing its importance in neural integration and communication.

Figure 7 DISC1 gene expression level in human brain

Although DISC1 expression in the choroid plexus, hippocampal formation, and cerebellum is lower relative to regions such as the thalamus and white matter, transcript levels in these areas (nearly 10 nTPM) remain robust and may support region-specific roles in cerebrospinal fluid regulation, memory processing, and motor coordination. Given that DISC1 has been linked to hippocampal function and synaptic plasticity, the relatively lower expression in this dataset indicates that its role in the hippocampus may be more dependent on protein interactions and subcellular localization rather than bulk RNA levels [12].

The moderate expression in the amygdala, basal ganglia, and midbrain suggests DISC1's involvement in emotional regulation, motor control, and reward pathways, which aligns with previous findings on its role in mood disorders and dopamine signaling pathways [1].

Figure 8 Median expression levels of the DISC1 gene across various brain regions

The median expression levels of the DISC1 gene vary across various brain regions, measured in RNA-seq counts per million (CPM) (**Figure 8**). The y-axis displays the log₂-transformed CPM values,

while the x-axis lists different brain regions. A red horizontal line at $\log_2(5)$ serves as a threshold for biologically meaningful gene expression. DISC1 is expressed at varying levels in different brain regions, with the highest expression observed in the parahippocampal gyrus (PHG), superior temporal gyrus (STG), and frontal pole (FP), while the cerebellum (CBE) exhibits the lowest expression. Notably, PHG, FP, and STG are brain regions implicated in cognitive function, memory processing, and neurodegenerative diseases such as AD. The PHG which exhibits the highest DISC1 expression in this dataset, is critically involved in episodic memory and spatial navigation [13]. It is also one of the earliest regions affected by neurofibrillary tangle accumulation in AD pathology [14]. The high expression of DISC1 in PHG suggests a potential role in maintaining neuronal integrity, and its dysregulation could contribute to the progressive memory loss characteristic of AD.

The FP and STG both show significant DISC1 expression. The FP, located in the prefrontal cortex, is associated with higher cognitive functions such as decision-making, problem-solving, and attention. In AD patients, atrophy in the FP has been correlated with impairments in recall abilities, indicating its involvement in memory deficits characteristic of the disease [15]. Similarly, the STG, situated in the temporal lobe, plays a crucial role in auditory processing and language comprehension. Research has shown that the STG is among the regions exhibiting significant gene expression abnormalities in individuals with mild to moderate dementia [16].

Single-Cell Analysis of DISC1 Expression Across Cell Types

Figure 9 Single-cell RNA expression level in multiple cell types for DISC1

Single-cell RNA-seq data from the HPA were analyzed to evaluate the cell-type-specific expression patterns of DISC1 across diverse tissues and cell types, providing a high-resolution view of its distribution. DISC1 expression levels, quantified in nTPM and visualized in the histogram (**Figure 9**), show a pronounced elevation in neuronal cells, particularly in rod photoreceptor cells, suggesting a specialized role in retinal function. In addition to its strong expression in photoreceptor cells, moderate DISC1 expression is observed in other neuronal cell types, including cone photoreceptors and bipolar cells, indicating potential functional significance beyond the central nervous system. The high expression in rod photoreceptors underscores its possible role in sensory processing and neuroprotective mechanisms in the visual system. Conversely, lower DISC1 expression is observed in glial cells, including Schwann cells,

suggesting a more limited role in myelination and glial-mediated support functions. However, its moderate presence in blood and immune cells implies a potential but less understood role in neuroimmune interactions, which could be relevant in neurodegenerative diseases such as AD [17].

Evolutionary Conservation and Species-Specific DISC1 Features

Researchers have analyzed DISC1 by cloning the cDNA from monkey brains and comparing it with various species including humans, rodents, and lower vertebrates [18]. The sequences of human and monkey DISC1 display remarkable similarity, with approximately 97% identity at the nucleotide level and 94% at the protein level [18]. This high conservation between primates stands in sharp contrast to the much lower conservation between human and rodent DISC1, which shows only about 60% identity both at nucleotide levels in the open reading frame and amino acid levels [18].

The conservation pattern of DISC1 is even lower in the N-terminal region, with only 45-50% similarity between humans and rodents [18]. This low sequence conservation is reminiscent of another gene involved in major mental illnesses, G72, which shows high homology between human and primate versions but has no identified rodent counterpart [18]. Bioinformatic cross-species comparisons have identified portions of DISC1 sequences in chicken and *Caenorhabditis elegans*, but researchers failed to find DISC1 in *Drosophila* [18]. These findings suggest that DISC1 may be a rapidly evolved gene in primates, possibly related to higher cognitive functions.

Despite significant sequence differences, the regional expression profile of DISC1 is well conserved between rodents and primates [18]. In both groups, DISC1 mRNA and protein expression are higher in the hippocampus and cerebral cortex regions, including frontal, parietal, temporal, and occipital cortices, and much lower in the cerebellum in adult brains [18]. This conservation of expression pattern is noteworthy considering that anatomical changes in the hippocampus and cerebral cortex have been frequently reported in brains from patients with schizophrenia. When examining DISC1 protein in monkey brains using Western blotting, researchers observed two distinct signals, similar to what has been found in human brains: a weaker signal at approximately 95 kDa and a stronger signal at approximately 70-80 kDa [18]. At least two major alternatively spliced variants of DISC1 were also detected in monkey brains by RT-PCR, including cDNA clones with or without exon 4, and two alternatively spliced products corresponding to human exon 11A and B [18].

The sequence conservation of DISC1 is substantially lower than that of genes for neurodegenerative diseases, such as presenilin-1 for AD [18]. This difference may suggest an overall pattern in the evolution of genes for psychiatric disorders versus neurodegenerative conditions. The researchers propose that although the main features of DISC1 may be conserved between rodents and primates, there may be minor functional changes or additions that exist between mice and humans [18].

DISC1 Splice Variants and Disease-Associated Mutations

The complex splicing patterns and numerous isoforms of DISC1 may have significant implications for AD pathology and treatment approaches. The various DISC1 isoforms, particularly those expressed during fetal development like $\Delta 3$, $\Delta 7\Delta 8$, and Esv1 transcripts, could influence neurodevelopmental processes that establish brain resilience or vulnerability to later neurodegenerative conditions like AD [19]. Since these variants encode truncated proteins lacking the C-terminus that mediates important protein-protein interactions, they may disrupt normal DISC1 function in ways that compromise neural integrity and create susceptibility to AD pathology.

The distinct temporal expression patterns of DISC1 splice variants, with highest expression during fetal development followed by dramatic downregulation after birth, suggests critical functions during early neurodevelopment [19]. This developmental regulation could establish neural networks with varying degrees of resilience to later AD-related insults. Targeting specific DISC1 splice variants that influence these early developmental processes might offer a novel preventative approach to AD.

Genetic variations in DISC1 associated with its splicing may represent risk factors shared between psychiatric disorders and AD. Polymorphisms like rs6675281 (Leu607Phe) and rs821616 (Cys704Ser), which affect expression of DISC1 transcripts, could potentially influence AD risk or progression through altered protein interactions or cellular functions [19]. These genetic associations might help identify individuals at heightened risk for developing AD, enabling earlier intervention. The dominant-negative effects of truncated DISC1 proteins observed in cell and animal models have implications for AD pathogenesis. Overexpression of C-terminally truncated DISC1 isoforms leads to disrupted protein interactions, mitochondrial dysfunction, and impaired neurite outgrowth [19]. These cellular abnormalities overlap with pathological processes in AD, suggesting that targeting specific DISC1 isoforms might mitigate neurodegenerative processes.

DISC1's role in neurite outgrowth and synaptic function makes it particularly relevant to AD, where synaptic loss is a major contributor to cognitive decline. Abnormal expression of specific DISC1 splice variants could impair synaptic maintenance and neuroplasticity, accelerating AD progression. Therapeutic strategies aimed at normalizing DISC1 isoform expression or function might preserve synaptic integrity and cognitive function in AD patients.

The developmental dysregulation of DISC1 splicing patterns associated with risk-related genetic variants suggests a potential window for early intervention [19]. If DISC1 splice variants influence early brain development in ways that affect susceptibility to later neurodegeneration, targeting these processes during critical developmental periods might establish greater neuronal resilience against AD pathology. DISC1's interactions with numerous proteins involved in cytoskeletal organization, neuronal migration, and intracellular signaling position it as a hub within cellular networks relevant to AD. Specific isoforms may differentially impact these protein interactions, making selective targeting of DISC1 variants a potentially precise approach to modulating pathways involved in AD pathogenesis without disrupting all DISC1 functions.

DISC1 Regulatory Networks and Protein Interactions

The regulatory networks involving DISC1 are complex and highly integrated with numerous cellular pathways, highlighting its pivotal role in neurodevelopment and its potential as a therapeutic target. DISC1 functions primarily as a scaffold protein, orchestrating the assembly and localization of multiple protein complexes, many of which are themselves implicated in psychiatric disorders [2].

Among the most extensively studied regulatory networks involving DISC1 are those linked to phosphodiesterase 4 (PDE4) and glycogen synthase kinase 3 β (GSK3 β). These pathways are of particular interest due to their therapeutic potential. DISC1 directly interacts with specific isoforms of PDE4 (PDE4B and PDE4D), with binding sites localized in the N-terminal region, which is largely disordered and structurally flexible, a property that may facilitate binding to multiple partners [19]. Notably, the N-terminal disordered regions of DISC1 overlap with several predicted and experimentally validated binding domains, including those for PDE4 isoforms, suggesting a dynamic regulatory capacity modulated by structural plasticity [19].

Similarly, DISC1 has been shown to bind GSK3 β , a kinase involved in numerous signaling pathways, including those regulating neurodevelopment and synaptic plasticity. This interaction implicates DISC1 in modulating downstream effects of GSK3 β , and inhibitors of GSK3 β , such as lithium, have demonstrated the capacity to partially reverse DISC1 mutation-related phenotypes in mouse models [19]. These findings support a model in which DISC1 serves as a molecular hub linking neurotransmission and neuroplasticity-related signaling cascades with cytoskeletal regulation and intracellular trafficking [19].

Importantly, the interaction domains for these proteins are often embedded within or adjacent to regions of predicted secondary structure in the C-terminal portion of DISC1, which is characterized by coiled-coil motifs and α -helices. These features suggest a dual regulatory mechanism in which structural motifs contribute to both the specificity and stability of DISC1's protein interactions [19].

Altogether, the DISC1 regulatory network encompasses over 200 potential protein interactors, many of which are components of converging signaling pathways relevant to psychiatric illness. Through its scaffold function, structural disorder, and regulatory associations with PDE4, GSK3 β , and other signaling molecules, DISC1 serves as a central integrator of neurodevelopmental signals, making it a promising molecular target in the treatment of AD [19].

DISC1-Mediated Signaling Pathways and Regulatory Mechanisms

DISC1 is a multifunctional scaffold protein that occupies a central position in several critical cellular pathways involved in neural development and signaling. Its interactions delineate a complex network of both upstream regulators and downstream effectors, making DISC1 a key node for modulating brain function and a promising target in AD research [20].

One of the most prominent pathways involving DISC1 is the Wnt/ β -catenin signaling cascade, where DISC1 serves as a negative regulator of GSK3 β . DISC1 binding inhibits GSK3 β activity, which prevents the degradation of β -catenin, allowing it to accumulate and translocate into the nucleus

to activate neurogenesis-related transcription through LEF/TCF factors [20]. In this context, upstream regulation involves proteins such as Dixdc1, which also interacts with DISC1 and is necessary to mediate these effects. Downstream, β -catenin acts as the transcriptional effector of this signaling cascade [20]. Notably, silencing of DISC1 or Dixdc1 reduces neural progenitor differentiation, which can be rescued by GSK3 β inhibitors or β -catenin expression, affirming DISC1's role as a critical upstream modulator of this pathway [20].

DISC1 also regulates the Akt/mTOR signaling pathway through its interaction with Girdin. Girdin normally enhances Akt activity, but DISC1 suppresses this effect by binding Girdin and blocking its function. This inhibition impacts downstream targets of Akt, such as mTOR, a key modulator of cellular growth and metabolism [20]. Overexpression of Girdin mimics the effects of DISC1 knockdown, leading to aberrant dendritic growth and neuronal migration, effects which can be rescued by mTOR inhibition using rapamycin [20]. Thus, DISC1 operates as an upstream brake on Akt/mTOR signaling by sequestering Girdin.

Another crucial pathway modulated by DISC1 is the cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP) signaling cascade. DISC1 interacts with all four subtypes of phosphodiesterase 4 (PDE4A-D), enzymes that degrade cAMP. DISC1 binds these enzymes in their low-activity states, thereby influencing cellular cAMP levels and modulating the downstream activation of PKA (protein kinase A) [20]. Among the downstream effectors are ATF4 and NDE1, both PKA substrates, implicating DISC1 in transcriptional regulation via CREB/ATF pathways [20]. Perturbations in this pathway have implications for mood disorders and cognitive deficits, further linking DISC1 to psychiatric and neurodegenerative disease mechanisms.

Upstream of DISC1, several signals can modulate its expression or activity. Neuregulin 1 (NRG1) and Neuregulin 2 (NRG2) enhance the expression of specific DISC1 isoforms through ErbB receptor-mediated pathways and BACE-dependent cleavage mechanisms. This process engages PI3K/Akt signaling and is transcriptionally driven [20]. Additionally, signaling by the neuropeptide PACAP increases DISC1 expression and stimulates its interaction with the zinc finger protein DBZ, further expanding the network of DISC1 modulation [20].

Collectively, these findings illustrate DISC1 as both a recipient of upstream regulatory inputs and a controller of downstream signaling outputs across multiple critical pathways. Through its modulation of Wnt/ β -catenin, Akt/mTOR, and cAMP/PKA signaling, DISC1 integrates diverse cellular signals into coherent neurodevelopmental and neuroplastic responses, roles that are particularly relevant for understanding and potentially treating AD [20].

Potential Off-Target Effects and Safety Considerations

In DISC1, certain interactions may be considered undesirable to target due to potential off-target effects. For instance, DISC1 interacts with dopamine D2 receptors (D2Rs), forming a complex that modulates D2R-mediated GSK3 β signaling and inhibits agonist-induced D2R internalization [21]. Disrupting this interaction has been shown to reverse behavioral deficits in a DISC1 mutant mouse model without inducing catalepsy, a predictor of extrapyramidal symptoms (EPS) in humans [21]. Therefore, while targeting the DISC1-D2R interaction may offer therapeutic benefits, caution is warranted to avoid unintended consequences associated with D2R

modulation. Similarly, DISC1's interaction with Kalirin-7 affects glutamatergic synapses via p21-activated kinases (PAKs). Selective PAK inhibitors have been used to prevent synaptic deterioration in DISC1 knockdown models [21].

Functional Studies Using DISC1 Knockout and Knockdown Models

Knockout (KO) and knockdown (KD) studies have been critical for elucidating the functional roles of DISC1 in the brain, particularly in relation to stress sensitivity, cognitive performance, and structural neuronal development. In a viral knockdown study conducted in adult rat prefrontal cortex (PFC), targeted reduction of DISC1 expression sensitized animals to stress-induced cognitive dysfunction. Rats with PFC-specific DISC1 KD exhibited significant working memory impairments following a mild one-hour restraint stress, a condition that did not affect control animals or those with DISC1 KD outside the PFC. This stress-specific vulnerability highlights DISC1's regulatory role in maintaining prefrontal network connectivity under adverse conditions [22]. The mechanism likely involves dysregulation of cAMP signaling pathways. DISC1 normally acts as a molecular anchor for PDE4, which degrades cAMP. Loss of DISC1 disrupts this anchoring, leading to elevated cAMP levels, excessive activation of HCN channels, and weakened synaptic connectivity, all of which impair working memory [22].

Complementary to these findings, studies using the DISC1^{Tm1Kara} mouse model, which carries a truncating mutation mimicking the schizophrenia-associated translocation, have provided valuable insight into the structural consequences of DISC1 loss. In cultured hippocampal neurons from these mice, both heterozygous and homozygous mutants exhibited reduced dendritic complexity, impaired axonal growth, and decreased spine density. These structural changes emerged early during neuronal maturation and were reversible with full-length DISC1 expression, indicating a direct, cell-autonomous effect of DISC1 deficiency [23]. In cortical neurons, the mutation selectively impaired dendritic spine development without significantly affecting dendritic or axonal arborization, suggesting a region-specific sensitivity to DISC1 levels [23].

Interestingly, the DISC1^{Tm1Kara} mutation preserves short N-terminal isoforms but eliminates the long forms that are essential for proper neuronal structure and function. The phenotypic similarity between heterozygous and homozygous mutants implies that DISC1 operates in a haploinsufficient manner, where one functional copy of the gene is insufficient for normal activity, an important consideration for understanding its contribution to AD [23].

Human iPSC Models and CRISPR-Mediated DISC1 Perturbation

Induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC) models utilizing CRISPR/Cas9 editing have emerged as a powerful approach to study the functional consequences of DISC1 mutations in human systems. Notably, two isogenic iPSC lines, TMOi001-A-5 and TMOi001-A-6, were generated by introducing precise mutations into exon 2 of the DISC1 gene using CRISPR/Cas9 technology. These mutations were designed to disrupt a region common to most DISC1 isoforms, thereby enabling the modeling of loss-of-function phenotypes in vitro [24].

The generated mutations include a heterozygous 5 bp deletion in TMOi001-A-5 and a compound heterozygous mutation in TMOi001-A-6, comprising a 17 bp deletion on one allele and a 1 bp

insertion on the other. Both mutations are predicted to cause frameshifts and introduce premature stop codons, likely resulting in loss of DISC1 protein function [25]. The use of single-cell sorting and Sanger sequencing confirmed the presence of these mutations, and rigorous off-target analysis across the top ten predicted sites showed no unintended genome modifications, confirming the high specificity of the editing strategy [25].

These CRISPR-edited iPSC lines maintain normal pluripotency, demonstrated by the expression of key markers such as NANOG, Sox2, and Oct4, as well as their capacity to differentiate into the three germ layers: ectoderm, mesoderm, and endoderm [25]. Importantly, both lines exhibited normal karyotypes and matched the parental line in short tandem repeat (STR) profiling, further supporting their genomic integrity and suitability for downstream applications [25].

The utility of these DISC1-mutant iPSCs lies in their ability to recapitulate human-specific aspects of disease biology that are not adequately modeled in animals. These cell lines offer a controlled, isogenic platform to investigate the cellular and molecular phenotypes associated with DISC1 dysfunction, including processes such as neuronal differentiation, migration, and synaptic connectivity [25].

DISC1 in AD: Current Evidence and Therapeutic Potential

Recent literature provides evidence supporting DISC1 as a potential therapeutic target in AD. Its expression is notably downregulated in AD brains, and overexpression has been shown to mitigate hallmark features of the disease, such as synaptic dysfunction and amyloid pathology [3].

In an AD cellular model expressing amyloid precursor protein (APP), DISC1 overexpression led to a 2.18-fold increase in protein levels and was associated with significant alterations in the proteome, including 351 differentially expressed proteins (DEPs) [3]. Proteomic and gene set enrichment analyses revealed that these DEPs were predominantly associated with microtubule organization, mitochondrial function, and protein translation, key pathways implicated in AD pathophysiology [3].

Importantly, protein–protein interaction analysis identified several high-confidence DISC1 interactors with potential relevance to AD, including NDE1 and KATNA1, which are involved in microtubule stability and neural development. The dysregulation of microtubule-associated processes is a known contributor to neurodegeneration, and the enrichment of cytoskeletal protein binding and microtubule-based processes in DISC1-overexpressing cells suggests a protective effect on the neuronal cytoskeleton [3]. DISC1 may help preserve microtubule integrity through its interactions with these partners.

DISC1 also modulates mitochondrial pathways, consistent with the mitochondrial cascade hypothesis of AD. High DISC1 expression correlated with downregulation of pathways involved in mitochondrial respiration and transmembrane transport, which may reflect the clearance of damaged mitochondria via DISC1-mediated mitophagy. This aligns with previous findings showing DISC1 functions as a mitophagy receptor, enabling the removal of dysfunctional mitochondria and thereby reducing oxidative stress [3].

Additional DISC1-interacting proteins relevant to AD include GRM3 and PTGER3. GRM3 encodes the metabotropic glutamate receptor 3 (mGluR3), whose activity supports synaptic plasticity and neuronal survival, processes that decline in AD. Downregulation of mGluR3 has been associated with cognitive impairment and increased susceptibility to amyloid toxicity, suggesting that DISC1 may exert neuroprotective effects through this pathway [3]. PTGER3, a receptor for prostaglandin E2, modulates neuroinflammation and cyclic AMP signaling, both of which are dysregulated in AD. Altered expression of PTGER3 in DISC1-overexpressing models suggests a role in modulating inflammatory responses and maintaining neuronal homeostasis [3].

Other enriched pathways in DISC1-overexpressing AD models include autophagy, heat shock protein (Hsp) signaling, and NMDA receptor trafficking, all relevant to the clearance of protein aggregates and maintenance of synaptic function. These findings suggest that DISC1 plays a multifaceted role in neuroprotection by coordinating responses to proteotoxic stress, preserving synaptic integrity, and maintaining cellular metabolism [3].

Structural Biology and Biophysics (SBB) Core: Structural Biology of DISC1

Following identification of DISC1 as a mechanistically relevant target, structural analysis reveals unique challenges and opportunities for therapeutic development. DISC1 functions as a multifunctional scaffold protein with distinct structural domains, including a disordered N-terminal region (residues 1-321) and α -helical C-terminal region (residues 322-854) that contains self-association, oligomerization, and dimerization domains (**Figure 10A**). AlphaFold3 predictions show the full-length monomeric structure with most α -helical regions predicted with high confidence, while experimental NMR structures are available for the C-terminal region complexed with binding partners like Ndel1 (**Figure 10B**). Of particular interest for small molecule targeting is the arsenic-binding C-X-C-X-C motif located at positions 680-684, where three cysteine residues create a potential druggable pocket (**Figure 10C**). Mutation studies have shown that residues C682 and C684 contribute more significantly to binding than C680, suggesting that small molecules could potentially bind deeply in this pocket near these critical cysteine residues. One of the known binding partners of DISC1 is nuclear distribution element-like protein-1 (NDEL-1) as DISC1-NDEL-1 binding is necessary for the migration of cortical neurons [26]. Schizophrenia-associated risk polymorphisms are located within the NDEL-1 binding region of DISC1 suggesting potential structural disruptions at this interface that may impair the assembly of neuronal migration complexes [26]. It has been shown using a combination of size exclusion chromatography and analytical ultracentrifugation that DISC1 initially forms a dimer and then assembles into an octamer [26]. DISC1 octamers interact with NDEL-1 tetramers, and this interaction appears to be mediated by secondary structural assemblies. A proposed DISC1 oligomerization and interaction model suggests that C-terminal domain is responsible for the dimerization and plays a crucial role in the assembly of DISC1 into higher-order oligomeric structures. Any alterations in the structural integrity of this region or any changes in the amino acid sequence can disrupt the proper oligomer formation. It has been shown that DISC1-S704C

polymorphism does not affect the dimer formation but instead promotes the assembly of a distinct higher-order oligomeric species [26].

Experimental structural determination of DISC1 has been elusive as the crystallization and cryo-EM on full length DISC1, or even on truncated versions of DISC1 has been unsuccessful in the past. This is likely in part due to the highly disordered N-terminal region. Also, DISC1 is challenging to purify as it is relatively insoluble and has a high propensity for forming aggregates. Consequently, maltose-binding protein (MBP) is usually fused to DISC1 to increase the solubility and various C-terminal constructs of DISC1 have been purified this way [26-28]. The only crystal structure of DISC1 is of a 15-residue short peptide (193-207 residues) of that was crystallized in complex with F-Box protein known as FBXW7. The DISC1 is known to bind to phosphodegron motif of FBXW7 and further protects DISC1 from degradation.

DISC1 is found intracellularly, localizing to the cytosol and intermediate filaments, and helps regulate neuronal intracellular trafficking [10]. In neurons, DISC1 is a regulator of mRNA, neurotransmitter receptors, mitochondrial motility, and numerous proteins and protein complexes. Protein-protein interactions with DISC1 occur along many regions, with some proteins interacting with the the N-terminal such as phosphodiesterase B1 and others interacting with the C-terminal of DISC1 including NDEL-1.

A study has shown that DISC1 functions as a negative regulator of the Akt/TOR pathway by sequestering its activator 'Girdin' thereby suppressing downstream translation process. However, this inhibitory role of DISC1 is reversed under oxidative stress conditions such as treatment with sodium arsenite showing the switch of DISC1 function from inhibitor to activator of protein synthesis. They also showed that DISC1 can directly bind arsenic via a C-terminal cysteine motif (C-X-C-X-C) located at positions 680–684 [28]. The three cysteine residues, highlighted in blue in **Figure 10**, show a potential binding site for small molecules. Upon mutation of the three cysteines in the C-X-C-X-C motif, C680 showed the lowest contribution towards binding of the three cysteine residues, suggesting that arsenic binds more deeply in the pocket near residues C682

Figure 10 Structural Features of DISC1 **A)** N- and C-terminal domains of DISC1. **B)** AlphaFold3 prediction of the full-length monomeric structure of DISC-1 (left). Most α -helical regions are predicted with high confidence. NMR complex of residues 765-835 of DISC1 with Ndel1 (right). PDB: 5YI4. **C)** Arsenic binding C-X-C-X-C region of DISC1 with cysteines shown in blue.

and C684. This study highlighted that DISC1 acts as an arsenic binding protein and all three cysteines are necessary for its role of cellular sensor.

Selectivity issues are expected when targeting DISC1 with small molecules. As a multifunctional scaffold protein, DISC1 interacts with over 200 proteins across distinct binding domains. Modulating one interaction may inadvertently affect others, making selective targeting challenging and increasing the risk of off-target effects [2]. To study DISC1 biophysically, it is important to assess the binding of DISC1 to its binding partners as well as its potential binding to small molecules. Because DISC1 has no enzymatic activity biophysical methods are recommended to elucidate its function [2]. Isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) would be a useful technique to assess DISC1 binding to small molecules and to binding partners and has been used in the past to assess DISC1 binding [29]. Mass photometry and Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) can be used to analyze the oligomeric states of DISC1. Mass photometry also allows use at low concentrations, so this helps decrease the likelihood of DISC1 aggregation which can occur at higher protein concentrations. Surface plasmon resonance (SPR) can also be used to understand its binding with small molecules and other partner proteins.

One of the primary issues surrounding DISC1 is the lack of any experimentally determined structure. The long N-terminal disordered tail of DISC1 makes structural determination of the full-length protein difficult, but important structural information could be determined from the specific regions of DISC1. The highly disordered portions of DISC1 make crystallization difficult, therefore, cryo-EM is likely a better option for attempting to obtain a structure of DISC1.

Structure-Function Studies Using DISC1 Domain Mutants

Studies of catalytically inactive and domain-specific DISC1 mutants have revealed critical insights into the molecular and cellular functions of DISC1, particularly its role in neuronal development and synaptic integrity.

Two different disease-associated DISC1 mutations were modeled in human iPSC-derived neurons to understand how distinct alterations affect neuronal biology. One mutation was engineered to mimic a balanced chromosomal translocation linked to psychiatric illness by introducing a frameshift in exon 8, and the second was a naturally occurring 4 base-pair deletion at the C-terminus in exon 12. These mutations result in truncated DISC1 proteins, effectively serving as domain mutants that disrupt specific regions of the protein without complete gene knockout [30].

The exon 8 frameshift mutant was found to cause reduced DISC1 protein expression via nonsense-mediated mRNA decay, while the exon 12 mutant likely produces an aggregation-prone protein that sequesters the wild-type protein, reducing functional DISC1 availability. Despite their different mechanisms, both mutants led to a similar reduction in overall DISC1 protein levels, pointing to a shared phenotype of DISC1 haploinsufficiency [30].

Importantly, functional consequences of these mutations were investigated through gene expression and proteomic profiling, which showed consistent downregulation of a small set of genes across both models. Most notably, UNC5D, a netrin receptor involved in neurite guidance and migration. Both DISC1 mutations led to impaired neurite outgrowth, a phenotype that could

be mimicked by UNC5D knockdown and rescued by targeted UNC5D upregulation using a catalytically inactive Cas9 (dCas9) fused to a transcriptional activator [30]. This approach underscores the utility of catalytically dead DISC1-related interventions as tools to probe compensatory mechanisms.

Moreover, proteomic analyses revealed changes in key neuronal proteins, including those involved in synaptic vesicle recycling and calcium signaling, although these were primarily detected in isogenic DISC1 exon 8 mutant models due to reduced variability. These subtle but consistent effects further support the role of domain-specific DISC1 disruptions in altering key pathways related to synaptic function and plasticity [30].

Assay Development and High Throughput Screening (ADHTS) Core: Assay Development and Feasibility for DISC1

As previously discussed, DISC1's established role as a scaffold protein underlies its functional relevance in synaptic and neuronal maintenance. Mice with point mutations in DISC1 were found to have shorter dendrites and decreased surface area and spine density in frontal cortical neurons [31] as well as reduced synaptic plasticity, specifically long-term potentiation (LTP) [32]. In humans, rare patient mutations in DISC1 led to synaptic deficits in cortical induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC) derived neurons [33]. Interestingly, PDE4 signaling was increased in this model and a rescue of synaptic dysfunction was achieved with PDE4 inhibitors [33]. There are more than 50 DISC1 isoforms found in the human brain. The developmental regulation of these isoforms suggests different splice variants are likely to have distinct functions [19].

Two single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), rs12044355 and rs6675281, from genome wide association studies (GWAS) identified DISC1 was associated with late onset AD (LOAD) risk [34, 35]. DISC1 is also found to be downregulated in AD postmortem brains [3, 4]. DISC1 and APP were co-immunoprecipitated together from mouse brain and interact through the N-terminal domain of DISC1 and intracellular region of APP [36]. Knockdown of DISC1 in rat primary neurons led to an increase in intracellular C-terminal fragment of APP and the corresponding secreted ectodomain product, as well as a significant decrease in A β 40 and A β 42 [37]. In this same study, these proteolytic changes were returned to homeostatic state by wild-type DISC1 but not a mutant variant lacking the amino acids required for interaction with APP, suggesting interaction with DISC1 is a critical event for the C-terminal processing of APP.

Previous studies have also indicated a relationship between DISC1, A β , and beta-site APP cleaving enzyme 1 (BACE1). Decreased DISC1 expression has been observed in APP/PS1 mice [4, 38], similar to AD brains, and cultured cells treated with A β oligomers [4]. In HEK293 cells, overexpression of DISC1 reduced protein BACE1 levels, but did not affect mRNA, whereas knockdown of DISC1 increased BACE1 protein [3, 38]. This rate of decline in BACE1 after DISC1 overexpression was attenuated by the lysosomal inhibitor chloroquine but not by the proteasome inhibitor MG-132, suggesting that DISC1 promotes lysosomal degradation of BACE1

to exert its protective effects against amyloid accumulation [38]. Similarly, AAV-mediated overexpression of DISC1 in the hippocampus of APP/PS1 mice showed reduced levels of BACE1, which are previously reported to be increased in APP/PS1 mice, reduced soluble A β 40/42 and amyloid plaque density, and rescued cognitive deficits [38].

Given the role DISC1 plays in major mental disorders, including schizophrenia and bipolar disorder, it is plausible that DISC1 dysfunction may also contribute to the cognitive dysfunction observed in AD. Our mechanistic hypothesis is that DISC1 is able to rescue A β induced neurodysfunction and increasing expression or function of DISC1 would be neuroprotective in AD.

DISC1 Functional Assessment and Quantification

DISC1 acts as a molecular scaffold, facilitating the assembly of multiple interacting proteins. While it lacks intrinsic enzymatic activity, its ability to multimerize may enable simultaneous binding of proteins that share overlapping DISC1 binding domains [32]. For instance, the C-terminal tail of DISC1 mediates self-association, which could be important for forming physiologically functional multimers [32].

However, under pathological conditions, DISC1 can form detergent-insoluble aggregates that localize to aggresomes. These aggregates, observed in post-mortem brain tissue from individuals with schizophrenia and mood disorders, fail to bind key partners such as NDEL1, suggesting a loss of normal DISC1 scaffold function [32]. While controlled multimerization may be essential for DISC1's physiological role, uncontrolled aggregation appears detrimental. Therapeutic strategies would ideally support functional assembly while preventing aggregation. Interactions with signaling proteins like PDE4, GSK3 β , or PCM1, could serve as surrogate markers of DISC1 scaffold function, providing insight into its biological activity and perturbation [21] [39].

Available Assays and Validation Status

DISC1 aggregation assays [40-42] can be used to understand the propensity to form aggregates and the impact of this on loss of DISC1 function and interaction with known binding proteins, including APP. One study looked at a single patient with schizophrenia and AD and found variations in DISC1 aggregates across different brain regions, suggesting a potential role in AD pathology [41]. One of DISC1's many functions include promoting neurite outgrowth [43, 44]. Reduced dendritic complexity [45, 46] as well as axonal degeneration [47, 48] are impacted in AD. Neurite outgrowth assays can be used to monitor the effect of DISC1 therapeutic targeting on restoring neurite outgrowth and function.

Microtubule organization assays [43] can be used to monitor the effects of DISC1 targeting on microtubule stabilization. Microtubule assembly and organization deficits have been reported in AD in tau-dependent and tau-independent mechanisms [49]. DISC1 is associated with microtubular dynamics and regulating neuronal migration and axonal formation as a part of the dynein motor complex. Reduced DISC1 function results in dissociation of this motor complex from the centrosome, resulting in reduced neurite outgrowth and disturbed neuronal migration.

Antibody Resources and Validation

Table 1 Commercially available antibodies for DISC1

Antibody	Vendor (Cat #)	Applications	Reference
DISC1 (B-2)	SantaCruz Biotech (sc-365591)	WB, IP, IF	
DISC1	R&D Systems (MAB6699)	ELISA, WB	
DISC1 (4U5N1)	Bio-Techne (NBP3-16462)	ICC/IF, WB	
DISC1	ThermoFisher (40-6800)	WB, IHC, ICC/IF, IP	[4]
DISC1	GeneTex (GTX31320)	WB, ICC/IF, ELISA	

Multiple commercially available antibodies provide validated tools for DISC1 detection across applications including Western blot (WB), immunoprecipitation (IP), immunocytochemistry (ICC/IF), and ELISA (**Table 1**). Many previous studies using DISC1 antibodies have developed them in house rather than purchasing from a vendor [50, 51]. Those that have used a commercial antibody do not provide specific catalog information. Reports have described the use of a DISC1 polyclonal antibody from Invitrogen but do not specify catalog number. Validated ISH probe sequences enable specific detection of DISC1 mRNA in mouse tissue (**Table 2**).

Table 2 In Situ Hybridization (ISH) using DIG-labeled RNA Probes for DISC1

ISH sequence	Species	Ref
Forward ATGCAGGGCGGGGGTCCCCGG	Mouse	[52]
Reverse TCAGGCCTCGGTTTCCTGAG		

Potential Anti-Targets and Selectivity Considerations

There are no known functional homologs of DISC1 in humans and it lacks any significant sequence homology with any other known proteins [53]. It is also possible that DISC1 interacting proteins also bind other proteins, scaffold or otherwise. Targeting DISC1 broadly through its interactome may impact the function of many cellular processes. However, targeting a specific interaction of DISC1 and one of its known binding partners, BACE1 or APP for example, may yield better results.

Cellular and Clinical Biomarker Recommendations

Several animal models have been developed to investigate DISC1 function. These include mice with Δ 2-3 exon deletions and a 25 bp deletion in exon 6 on a C57BL/6 background [54], as well as doxycycline-inducible Δ hDISC1 constructs under the CaMKII promoter enabling forebrain-restricted expression [55]. Additional models include C-terminally truncated human DISC1 transgenes [56], 4-bp exon 12 deletion knock-ins [57], and mice bearing point mutations such as Q31L [30] and L100P [31, 58]. Bilateral AAV-mediated overexpression of DISC1 in the hippocampus of 4-month-old APP/PS1 mice has also been used to examine functional rescue effects [38].

Table 3 RNA Interference Reagents Targeting DISC1

siRNA targeting sequences	Species/Cell type	Ref
siRNA-1 GGCTACATGAGAAGCACAG	Rat oligodendrocyte precursor cells	[52]
siRNA-2 CTGGCTGATGCGAGAGAAA		
shRNA #1- strong suppression GGCAAACACTGTGAAGTGC	Rat PC12 cells and mouse brain slices	[43]
shRNA #2- mild suppression CGGCTGAGCCAAGAGTTGG	<i>No effect on human DISC1 expression</i>	
siRNA Sense GGCAGAUGGAUGACUUAGATT	Human	[38]
Anti-sense UCUAAGUCAUCCAUCUGCCTT		
siRNA Sense GGCAAACACUGUGAAGUGCTT	Mouse	
Anti-sense GCACUUCACAGUGUUUGCCTT		
siRNA Sense UUCUCCGAACGUGUCACGUTT	Non targeting control	
Anti-sense ACGUGACACGUUCGGAGAATT		
siRNA Sense GGCAGAUGGAUGACUUAGATT		[4]
Anti-sense UCUAAGUCAUCCAUCUGCCTT		

Several cell line models have been utilized to investigate DISC1 function in disease-relevant contexts. Patient-derived iPSCs carrying a chromosomal translocation t(1;11)(q42;q14) affecting DISC1 have been used to study the impact of structural mutations on neuronal development and connectivity [59]. Additional iPSC lines have been generated with CRISPR/Cas9-mediated disruptions in exon 8 or exon 2 of DISC1 [60], enabling precise modeling of loss-of-function variants. HEK293-APP cells transduced with DISC1-expressing lentiviral constructs have provided a system to study DISC1's interaction with amyloid precursor protein and its downstream effects on A β processing [3]. Moreover, iPSC-derived neurons harboring patient-specific mutations, including a 4-bp deletion within the DISC1 locus and a translocation breakpoint, have offered platforms for assessing isoform-specific dysfunctions in DISC1 biology and synaptic phenotypes [57]. Lentiviral-mediated knockdown of DISC1 has been achieved using constructs expressing

shRNA in primary cortical neurons derived from mouse and rat models [37]. Multiple siRNA and shRNA sequences targeting DISC1 have been validated in different species and cell types, with varying degrees of knockdown efficiency (**Table 3**).

Quantitative PCR Resources for DISC1 Analysis

Validated RT-qPCR primers for DISC1 have been developed across human, mouse, and rat species to enable precise amplification of transcript-specific regions (**Table 4**). For human DISC1, the NCBI Gene ID is 27185, and the reference mRNA sequence for isoform L is NM_018662.3. In mouse, DISC1 isoform 1 is annotated under Gene ID 244667, with the corresponding mRNA reference sequence NM_174854.2. The coding sequence (CDS) homology between mouse and human DISC1 is approximately 69%.

For rat DISC1, the gene is listed under NCBI Gene ID 307940, with transcript variant 5 represented by mRNA reference sequence XM_063278075.1. The DISC1 CDS exhibits about 67% homology between rat and human, and 87% between rat and mouse. All primer sequences used in these studies were derived from the literature and verified against the respective mRNA coding sequences using BLAST alignment to ensure specificity and conservation across species.

Table 4 PCR Primer Sequences for DISC1 Across Species and Experimental Contexts

Primer sequence	Targeted species	Ref
Exons 2-3 Forward GAATGTGGCACGGTC TCCTC Reverse TAATCGCCATCCTCGACCAC	Mouse	[54]
Exons 7-10 Forward TGGCTGTCAGAGAACTCACTGCTCAG Reverse CCATGCACTTCACAGTGTTCCTTCA		
Exon 11-12 Forward TGGCTGTCCCTAGAACACCC Reverse CTCATGCCTATGGCTTCGC	Rat	[52]
Exon 5-6 Forward TGATGCGAGAGAAAGAGCAA Reverse AGCATCTCCTGATCCTCAA		
Forward CaMKII: ATTCGCTGTCTGCGAGGGCC Reverse human DISC1: TCTCACAGAGGTCACAGTAGGGGCTGCTGCAC Reverse complement of reverse DISC1 primer: GTGCAGCAGCCCCTACTGTGACCTCTGTGAGA	Human (via overexpression under CamKII promoter)	[56]
Exon 2 Forward CCCCTACTGTGACCTCTGTGA Reverse AATCTGGTGCCACCTCTGA	Human (iPSC)	[60]
Exon 12/13 Forward AAAGTGTGAAGACATAGGCAAGAA Reverse CCCTCCTGAGAGAATGAATGAG		
Forward GCACCCTGAGGAAGAAAGTT Reverse TCTCTTCTCAGTCTGTTGTAATCT	Human	[38]
Forward GCACTTTGCGGTTTCATTCAA Reverse GGAGCCAGAGACTTAAAGCTG	Mouse	[4]

Medicinal Chemistry and Chemical Biology (MCCB) Core: Modality Selection and Identification of Chemical Probes

DISC1 Natural Ligands and Substrates

DISC1 lacks enzymatic activity and does not possess a known natural ligand or substrate, consistent with its role as a multifunctional scaffold protein [61].

Chemical Probe Availability

DISC1 is not a conventionally druggable target with a small molecule approach due to its lack of enzymatic activity and an unresolved 3D structure. However, several DISC1 interacting proteins, such as PDE4, GSK3 β , and components of the AKT1/mTOR pathway, are well-established drug targets with available modulators. These proteins have been investigated extensively in the context of psychiatric, inflammatory, and oncological disorders [62]. Targeting interactions within the DISC1 complex, such as the DISC1-PDE4 interaction, offers a strategy to modulate signaling pathways while avoiding off-target effects of global inhibition [63]. Recent evidence also shows that DISC1 function is regulated via phosphorylation, opening possibilities for indirect modulation [64]. Although direct targeting of DISC1 remains challenging, especially without structural data, rational design strategies may become feasible in the future. In the meantime, leveraging existing probes for DISC1-associated proteins presents a practical approach to interrogating its biological functions and therapeutic relevance in neuropsychiatric diseases [65].

Selectivity Challenges and Considerations

Selectivity poses a significant challenge when targeting DISC1 and its interactome. Modulating one interaction may inadvertently affect others, leading to unintended consequences. For instance, DISC1's interaction with GSK3 β has been shown to inhibit its activity; however, designing modulators that selectively target this interaction without affecting other GSK3 β functions would be challenging. Similarly, targeting the DISC1-PDE4 complex requires caution, as PDE4 isoforms are widely expressed and involved in various cellular processes, raising concerns about undesired effects [66]. Therefore, achieving specificity in modulating these DISC1 interactions necessitates a nuanced understanding of its interactome and the development of specific assays correlated to cellular pharmacology and *in vivo* pharmacodynamics leading to desired efficacy and safety *in vivo* [43].

Therapeutic Modality Recommendations

Upon reviewing the available literature, there is limited information on the development of therapeutic modalities targeting DISC1, such as small molecules, antibodies, or siRNA. DISC1 interacts with multiple partners and influences several psychiatric disease pathways, but the lack of a resolved 3D structure hinders rational drug design [1]. The modulation of DISC1 function *via* phosphorylation has been proposed as an indirect strategy, and small molecule approaches might need to focus on altering its interactions rather than targeting DISC1 directly.

Gene-silencing approaches such as siRNA are not suitable for DISC1 in the context of AD, where therapeutic strategies would aim to enhance rather than suppress DISC1 expression. While siRNA has been used in mechanistic studies of DISC1 function, its application as a therapeutic modality

would be counterproductive unless targeting a negative regulator of DISC1. Future RNA-based approaches might instead focus on targeting upstream repressors of DISC1. Challenges remain regarding delivery to the central nervous system and off-target effects. Antibody-based therapies also face limitations due to the intracellular localization of DISC1.

DISC1 Pharmacological Landscape and Therapeutic Approaches

Given that DISC1 has no enzymatic activity, there are no direct inhibitors of its function. However, previous studies have investigated disruption of DISC1 with its binding proteins, dopamine receptor 2 (DR2) and Kalirin-1 for example [21]. Administration of an interfering peptide that disrupted the DR2-DISC1 complex was able to reverse behavioral deficits in a DISC1-L100P mouse schizophrenia model [58]. However, in the context of AD, the therapeutic goal is likely to restore or enhance DISC1 function, potentially by stabilizing its interactions or increasing expression. Targeting the DISC1 interactome may offer a means to modulate its neuroprotective roles in AD.

Additionally, an increase in DISC1 expression in mouse brains was observed after treatment with atypical antipsychotics olanzapine and risperidone but was not observed with the typical antipsychotic haloperidol [67], suggesting current FDA-approved drugs could be repurposed for targeting DISC1. Targeting the stability of DISC1 is also a potential therapeutic approach to increase its function and mitigate the loss of DISC1 function caused by its aggregation. For example, the half-life of DISC1 was increased in PC12 cells by co-expression of PDE4B2, a PDE4 isoform, whereas in contrast hypoxic stress drastically reduced DISC1 protein levels [21].

Although there is research suggesting DISC1 regulates the GSK3 β pathway [2], and thereby may influence tau hyperphosphorylation associated with AD [68], inhibitors of GSK3 have yet to show success in clinical trials. DISC1 is also involved in mitochondrial homeostasis, through ATP production and calcium buffering, and is distributed on the outer and inner mitochondrial membranes [69]. It also regulates axonal trafficking of mitochondria [70]. Recent evidence has also suggested that DISC1 is directly involved in mitophagy, a process that is compromised in AD [71], and acts as a mitophagy receptor [4]. DISC1 binds directly to LC3-I/II and overexpression of DISC1 induces mitophagy in an LC3 dependent manner and rescues A β -induced mitochondrial dysfunction. Knockdown of DISC1 was able to block mitophagy induced by A β in primary rodent cortical neurons. AAV-mediated overexpression of DISC1 in 8-month-old APP/PS1 mice restored mitochondrial function and rescued cognitive deficits.

Conclusions and Recommendations for Targeting DISC1

This Target Enabling Package provides comprehensive evidence supporting DISC1 as a mechanistically relevant therapeutic target for AD through an integrated computational and experimental pipeline. The systematic identification of DISC1 across independent drug repurposing analyses, combined with its consistent upregulation by the pharmacological agent trichostatin-A (TSA) in multiple experimental contexts, establishes a foundation for therapeutic development. Our findings demonstrate that DISC1 represents a convergent mediator of neuroprotective pathways, uniquely positioned at the intersection of neuronal protection, microglial homeostasis, and synaptic maintenance.

DISC1 expression is significantly downregulated in AD brains, and experimental restoration provides neuroprotective benefits through multiple complementary mechanisms including synaptic integrity preservation, mitochondrial function enhancement, and amyloid processing regulation. The protein's central positioning within extensive protein networks regulating over 200 interactions, while presenting selectivity challenges, also offers numerous potential therapeutic entry points. Functional validation in human iPSC-derived neuronal models confirms that DISC1 upregulation by TSA maintains protective effects even in the presence of A β toxicity, suggesting robust therapeutic potential.

However, significant challenges remain for direct therapeutic targeting of DISC1. As a multifunctional scaffold protein lacking enzymatic activity and with limited high-resolution structural characterization, traditional small molecule approaches face substantial obstacles. The protein's extensive interactome presents both opportunities for pathway modulation and risks for undesired effects that could compromise therapeutic selectivity. Furthermore, the need to enhance rather than reduce DISC1's functions requires more complex approaches to activation compared with the more straightforward development of inhibitors.

While direct modulation through conventional small molecules, antibodies, or siRNA remains challenging, our research clearly indicates that increased DISC1 levels confer therapeutic effects, warranting the development of innovative treatment strategies that can effectively enhance DISC1 function. The diversity of DISC1's roles across multiple cell types, combined with the complexity of developing agonistic modulators for scaffold proteins, suggests that immediate therapeutic pursuit may be premature without additional foundational research. Future efforts should prioritize structural characterization of key DISC1 domains and protein complexes, development of quantitative assays for AD-relevant DISC1 functions, identification of druggable protein-protein interactions within the DISC1 interactome, and exploration of indirect modulation strategies through upstream regulators or downstream effectors.

The comprehensive evidence presented in this TEP establishes DISC1 as a mechanistically important protein whose modulation could offer significant therapeutic benefits in AD through restoration of synaptic integrity, mitochondrial function, and cellular homeostasis. Once specific DISC1 functions can be appropriately quantified in AD contexts and innovative targeting approaches for scaffold proteins continue to evolve, this target should be revisited with high priority. The combination of robust biological rationale, extensive experimental resources, and strategic development framework positions DISC1 for future therapeutic pursuit as methodological advances in protein-protein interaction targeting continue to evolve.

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